

Level of Stress Among Students of Southern Capital Colleges: Basis for Instructional Management Plan

Bejie M. Emperio

Master of Arts in Education (MAED) major in Educational Management
Southern Capital Colleges, Oroquieta City, Philippines

Abstract:- The outbreak of the pandemic COVID-19 introduced students to new and stressful college experiences. The transition from traditional learning modes to flexible learning delivery had been stressful for students. In light of this, this study aimed to investigate the level of stress among students of Southern Capital Colleges as basis for instructional management plan. Descriptive –correlational research design was used to assess the students' stress level. A total of 259 students completed two sets of questionnaires collecting their demographic profile and assessing their stress level on four stress-related factors (personal, relationship, academic, and environmental). The results revealed that the students experienced moderate level of stress. Among the four stress-related factors, the stress levels of the students were shown to be primarily influenced by academic and environmental stressors. The study revealed that the students' demographic profile in terms of age, program, year, number of enrolled units, and academic performance were significantly correlated with their level of stress. Furthermore, multiple regression analysis was employed to find out which among the student profiles best predicted their level of stress. It showed that age, number of enrolled units, and academic performance significantly predicted respondents' level of stress. With all the variables taken in this study, it can be inferred that the students' stress level had a negative effect to their academic performance. Thus, the findings of this research are highly recommended and the proposed instructional management plan may give insights to academic planners on how to deliver high-quality academic programs and services and make the learning environment proactive to learning.

Keywords:- *Level of Stress, Stress-Related Factors, Academic Performance, Institutional Management Plan.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The surge of the pandemic COVID-19 had brought many challenges to every college student may it be school-related, personal experiences, or family-related problems. These challenges brought forth new experiences that college students were not accustomed to. The transition from the traditional mode of learning to the flexible mode of learning delivery had been a struggle for most students. This challenging learning situation had caused negative consequences to their academic, psychological, and physical well-being. Thus, the present study sought to explore the

level of stress among students and its effect to academic success.

Stress is inevitable in student life and a common problem for every individual college student. Kumari, et al. (2009) and Silverman, et al. (2010) defined stress as a natural reaction of the body to any change or demand which needs an immediate response, regulation, and or emotional adjustment. Suleyman and Zewdu (2010) highlighted that too much pressure exceeds a person's coping ability; it is where stress comes in. Prolonged stress shuts down a person's ability to cope with ordinary situations and sets up distress. If not given substantial attention, students' physical health, emotional well-being, and academic performance are at risk. For a holistic and successful readjustment, an individual needs to maintain harmony between situational demands and biophysical resources (Sarafino, 2002) as well as gain stability in the moment of change as body stress systems are activated in a response to high levels of stress (McEwen, 2004).

Essel and Owusu (2017) identified four major causes of stress namely relationship, environmental, academic, and personal factors. Similarly, Buló and Sanchez (2014) identified intrapersonal, interpersonal, academic, and environmental stressors affecting college students in dealing with their family, friends, and significant others, interpersonal and environmental stressors ranked the highest and lowest respectively. In addition, Dy, et al. (2013) found out that the major stressors of the students were academic difficulty, workload, time management, and personal responsibilities.

Furthermore, many researchers had examined the effect of stress on the academic performance of the students (Aihie & Ohanaka, 2019; Reddy, et al. 2018; Feldman, et al. 2008; Simpson 2018; Palacio, et al. 2013; Mustafa, 2004; Lemay, 1993). The findings of these studies showed that high level of stress was associated with low achievement and was significantly correlated to each other.

Thus, given the learning situation wherein the students are currently experiencing right now and the ongoing challenges posed by the pandemic not just to the educational setting but as well as to the social and economic settings, this study focused on examining the level of stress of college students of Southern Capital Colleges in terms of stress-related factors such as relationship, personal, academic, and environmental. It further examined student's

stress based on demographic profiles such as gender, age, program and year of study, number of units enrolled and monthly income of the family. This study hoped to give reliable results that could serve as basis for instructional management plan.

➤ *Statement of the Problem*

This study was conducted to determine the level of stress among college students of Southern Capital Colleges as basis for instructional management plan during First Semester 2021-2022. Specifically, the study attempted to answer the following research questions:

- What was the profile of the respondents in terms of their:
 - ✓ Gender,
 - ✓ Age,
 - ✓ Program,
 - ✓ Year level,
 - ✓ Number of enrolled units,
 - ✓ Monthly income of the family, and
 - ✓ Academic performance?
- What was the mean distribution of respondents in terms of stress-related factors?
- What was the stress level of the respondents?
- Was there a correlation between the respondents' level of stress and their demographic profile?
- Was there a relationship existed between the respondents' level of stress and their demographic profile?
- What instructional management can be developed from the findings of the study?

➤ *Theoretical Framework*

This study was heavily influenced by Hans Selye's General Adaptation Syndrome (1936) and Richard Lazarus' Transactional Model of Stress and Coping (1966). Hans Selye postulates that stress arises when the body's natural homeostatic mechanisms fall short of giving it the tools it needs to adjust to the demands placed on it. The general adaptation syndrome is a widespread physical response to stress. The mobilization might be so extensive that it impairs the body's regular functioning.

The general adaptation syndrome has three stages namely alarm reaction stage, stage of resistance, and stage of exhaustion. The alarm reaction stage is characterized by an individual's momentarily immobilization, for example, in a condition of shock, there is a rapid and intensive mobilization of physical resources, including a high level of visceral and skeletal muscle activity. In the stage of resistance, it is the individual's period of recovery and restoration of balance as well as adapting to the stress. Outwardly, it appears to be a tranquil stage, but the endocrine glands, particularly the anterior pituitary and adrenal cortex, are hard at work assisting the individual in adapting "to the stressful situation". The stage of exhaustion is characterized by the occurrence of exhaustion and the recurrence of alarm reaction because of the continued stress and the individual's inability to maintain the resistance

level. If stress persists, serious injury or even death may occur.

The Transactional Model of Stress and Coping (Lazarus, 1966) focuses on individual's varied impulses to his environment and for appraising progressions of coping to stressful situations. It deals with a person's perception relative to stress whether an event is threatening or challenging. These stressful situations or events are viewed as person-environment transactions depending on the intensity of the stressors and the individual's coping ability. He stressed that an individual must first make an appraisal to the stressor and second on the person's social and cultural disposal.

According to Whitman, et al. (1984), the transactional model of stress is appropriate in illustrating the effect of various stressors such as academic, personal, environment, etc. Since, this model is a set of affective, cognitive, and adaptive responses, it arises from person-environment transaction. Richard Lazarus pinpointed that the person and the environment are inseparable, thus, each one affects the other.

Thus, given the above mentioned-points pinpointed by Hans Selye's General Adaptation Syndrome and Richard Lazarus' Transactional Model of Stress and Coping, it is imperative for every individual to examine every situation that threatens or challenges his/her response to a stressful situation. For a more realistic response, every individual needs to know his/her capacity and limitations as a person.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

➤ *Definition of Stress*

The word stress is a form of the Middle English *destresse*, derived via Old French from the Latin "stringere", to draw tight (Eduardo et al. (2015). The term was first coined by Hans Selye, an endocrinologist, in a biological context in the 1930s. In his book, the *Stress of Life* (1956) as cited in Hill (2014), he defined stress as "any nonspecific demand placed upon the body". Eduardo, et al. (2015) defined stress as the failure of an organism to respond appropriately to emotional or physical threats, whether actual or imagined. It is used loosely in everyday conversation (Lazarus, et al. 1985; as cited in Zimbardo, et al. 2003). Commonly, stress refers to a situation wherein modern society is associated and linked.

In addition, Hanson (1987) in his book "The Joy of Stress" viewed stress as an individual reaction. It can be fantastic or it can be fatal. It is all up to the individual. Too much stress, however, can be negative force. Too little stress can be just as disastrous. According to Galindez (2011), an event is considered stressful when there are traumas outside the range of normal human experience, perceived as uncontrollable or unpredictable, challenge the limits of a person's capabilities and causes internal conflicts.

In a theoretical perspective, Hans Selye (1976) who proposes the response theory of stress defined stress as the physiological response of the body to any demand placed on it. While Lazarus & Folkman (1984) proposed that stress involves the perception of stressors in relationship to the coping resources available to use in the management of stress. The above perspectives are incorporated by Melgosa (2004) as physiological and psychosocial responses by individuals to stressors that tax their coping abilities.

➤ *Detrimental Effects of Stress*

The continued threat brought by the pandemic COVID-19 as well as the unprecedented conditions with regards to the academic, social, economic, and personal aspects may have increased students' stress level. Limited stress is beneficial and can lead to excellent performance, however, uncontrolled stress can lead to exhaustion, depression, and several other sicknesses (Essel & Owusu, 2017). According to Okoro (2018), there are three (3) detrimental effects of stress namely depression, anxiety, and insomnia.

Depression is an emotional state which is marked by great sadness and apprehension, feeling of worthiness and guilt, detachment from others, lack of sleep, appetite, and sexual drive, loss of interest and pleasure in regular activities (Kring, et al. 2010). In addition, Farabaugh, et al. (2012) & Ibrahim, et al. (2013) defined depression as a multi-faceted problem that leads to impairment in interpersonal, social, and occupational functioning and is often happen among college students. In a study conducted by Alsubaie, et al. (2019), 33% out of 461 student-respondents experienced depressive symptoms. Moreover, social support from family and friends was identified as a significant predictor of depressive symptoms. In addition, a nationwide cross-sectional survey on depressive symptoms among young adults in the Philippine showed 8.9% of young Filipino adults experienced moderate to severe depressive symptoms and the prevalence was higher in females than males with 10.2% and 7.6% respectively (Puyat, et al. 2019).

Anxiety is explained as the manner in which a person reacts or response to stress, accept and interpret (May, 2015). In this manner, stress is seen as a journey to anxiety, thus, anxiety is the product of stress and it reflects how an individual handles stress.

Insomnia is defined as "a chronic or acute sleep disorder characterized by a complaint of trouble beginning and/or maintaining sleep, as well as a subjective complaint of poor sleep quality resulting in daytime impairment and subjective report of impairment" (Roth, 2007). A study of Smith, et al. (1998) found symptoms of anxiety, depression and, or stress which fall outside the normal range among 25% of 11 year old and 31% of 12 year old students. Statistically, more females than males had experienced these symptoms. Also, results showed that there were correlations between stress and depression ($r = .59, p < .05$) ($r = .70, p < .01$), stress and anxiety ($r = .67, p < .05$) ($r = .64, p < .01$) in 11 and 12 year old students respectively.

➤ *Sources of Stress*

Students' lives have unique cluster of stressful experiences. These experiences affect student's academic performance directly or indirectly in many ways. According to Bernstein, et al. (2008), sources of stress refer to all threatening circumstances or events that cause people to make adjustments from disrupting impulses. The sources of stress are called stressors; internal or external environment that distract the balance of the well-being of an individual which requires immediate action to restore balance (Lazarus & Cohen, 1977 as cited in Rana, 2019). The degree of severity and duration of stress differ from every individual; what is stressful to an individual may not be stressful to other. Phinney and Haas (2003) stressed out sources of stress among students such as difficult financial challenges, domestic responsibilities, responsibilities related to holding a job while in school, and a heavy academic load. Similarly, Cherian and Charian (1998) found that the main source of students stress in terms of intensity was related to the studies, work, career, sensitivity, confidence, family, economic problems, lack of facilities, mild neurosis, sex, marriage, self-schedule, independence, social problems, health, and self-image.

In addition, Pereira (1997) presented four main categories of the sources of stress: personal problems which include homesickness, loneliness, suicide, shyness, family problems; academic problems include lack of motivation, examination stress, withdrawal and drop out, academic work, facilities, lectures, other students, ethnic problems; financial and housekeeping problems; and security problems (sexual assault, violence at student social events, bullying, drugs and alcohol). Yumba (2008) and Essel & Owusu (2017) identified four categories of stressors namely relationship, personal, and environmental stress.

Relationship Stress. Relationship is defined as a social bond between and among individuals manifested through communication and other forms of interaction (Peralta, et al. 2019). This bond may be biological or determined by social contracts such as social consensus or laws. Relationship-related problems were listed by American College Health Association (2012), as the third leading source of stress. These include change in a relationship, conflicts with a roommate, working with people you don't know, contact with strangers and family problems. In a study conducted by Petroff (2008), the findings reveal negative correlation between stress and relationships which mean if individuals shared a happy and healthy relationship, stress is decreased.

Personal Stress. According to Australian Bureau of Statistics, personal stressors are events or conditions that occur in a person's life that may adversely impact on the individual's health or wellbeing. A stressor may occur directly such as personal experience that may have an ongoing impact or limit the capacity of a person, or family, to live a satisfying and productive life. Soomro, et al. (2019) stressed that personal stress is one of the main sources of stress among students. This includes change in living environment, change in sleeping habits, new responsibilities,

financial difficulties, combining job with studies, health problems and poor eating habit.

Academic Stress. Stankovska, et al. (2008) defined academic stress as the anxiety and stress that come from schooling and education. Pursuing a degree in one's education is often a lot of pressure as it involves studying, homework, tests, labs or reading, and time management among these activities. Academic stress can be conceptualized as a student's interaction between environmental stressors, the cognitive appraisal of the academic related stressors and coping with them, and psychological or physiological response to the stressors (Mire & McKean, 2000). Academic related stressors include increased class workload, lower grade, many hours or insufficient time to study, the workload in a semester, and the results from exams.

In similar sense, Hashim (2003) & Tyrrel (1992) as cited in Khanekhesi & Basavarajappa (2011) identified academic stress as a significant source of stress for many students covering not only examinations but also other academically related stressors such as fear of logging behind in the homework, writing assignment, working on individual and group projects, time pressure, lack of financial support, concern about academic ability, scheduling classes and required motivation to study. For many students, the pursuit of higher education is a time of transition marked by a set of demands germane to the setting.

Environmental Stress. The transition of students from school environment to college environment could cause a psychological, academic and social shock, since this educational system has huge differences (Yikealo, et al. 2018). In this level, students face new methods of teaching, new academic requirements, new type of relations between students and faculties and even new relations among students themselves. Due to these changes, the student's wellbeing is affected as they potentially experience different types of stress. Rajasekar (2013) as cited in Yikealo, et al. (2018) considered faculty treating peer groups differently, mingling with peers of different race/ethnicity on campus, finding support groups sensitive to specific needs, living in the local community, adjusting to the campus environment, participating in class and meeting with faculty as constituents of environmental stress.

Thus, in the context of the growing body of literature about stress and its related issues revealed in the above written literature, stress, in general, poses a big threat to a person's homeostasis if not given proper actions. This literature review provides evidences that signify a person's collective and proactive response to his or her environment as it affects one another. It is a challenge to every person to look after every factor that affects a person's well-being in order to function willfully and responsively.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This study used the descriptive-correlation method of research. In educational research, descriptive research is beyond mere gathering and tabulation of data. It involves the elements or interpretation of the meaning or significance of what is described. This study aimed to determine the level of stress and the predictors of stress among students of Southern Capital Colleges as basis for instructional management plan.

B. Participants of the Study

Out of the 734 undergraduate students, a total of 259 students was identified as respondents in the study coming from the three (3) undergraduate programs of Southern Capital Colleges namely Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEEd), Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA), and Bachelor of Science in Criminology (BS Criminology). All of the respondents were officially enrolled in the First Semester of Academic Year 2021-2022.

C. Sampling Procedure

The sampling method or procedure used in getting the number of respondents was stratified sampling. This sampling design was appropriate to the given respondents as it ensures the proportionality of the sample size to each stratum. Slovin's formula was used to compute for the adequate sample size.

D. Research Instruments

In this study, the researcher utilized two sets of questionnaires. These were: 1) Questionnaire Checklist on the Socio-Demographic Profile of Student-Respondents, and 2) Questionnaire Checklist on Student Stress Inventory (SSI). The first is the Profile of Student-Respondents Questionnaire Checklist. It collects information on gender, age, program, year of study, number of units enrolled, and monthly income of the family.

The second questionnaire, which is adopted from Student Stress Inventory which is developed by Mohamed Arip, et al. (2016) and validated by a panel of nine experts based on their expertise, is composed of forty negative items categorized under four stress-related issues, namely: 1) personal/physical, 2) interpersonal relationship, 3) academic, and 4) environmental factors. The questionnaire is scored using an ordinal scale, with 1 for 'Never', 2 for 'Somewhat Frequent', 3 for 'Frequent', and 4 for 'Always'. The scores are interpreted as 40-80 for 'mild stress', 81-121 for 'moderate stress', and 122-160 for 'severe stress'.

E. Statistical Treatment

The data gathered were tabulated, tallied and analyzed for in-depth interpretation to produce accurate information. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, and mean were used to organize the results. Pearson correlation coefficient was utilized to determine if there is a significant association between student profile and their level of stress. Multiple regression analysis was also employed to find out

which among the student profiles best predicts their level of stress.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents’ profile. It can be seen in the table that out of the 259 respondents, 150 or 57.9% were males and 109 or 42.1% were females. Regarding age, 89 or 34.4% of the respondents were 18-19 years old; 107 or 41.3% were 20-21 years old; 40 or 15.4% were 22-23 years old; and 23 or 8.9% were 24 years old and above. In terms of program of study, 16 or 6.2% were Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd); 51 or 19.7% were Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA); and 192 or 74.1% were Bachelor of Science in Criminology (BSCriminology). About year of study, 138 or 53.3% were first year; 57 or 12.0% were second year; 38 or 14.7% were third year; and 26 or 10.0% were fourth year. Relating to number of enrolled units, 39 or 15.1% were enrolling below

18 units; 51 or 19.7% were enrolling 19-22 units; 60 or 23.2% were enrolling 23-26 units; and 109 or 42.1% were enrolling 27 and above units. Concerning monthly income of the family, 203 or 78.4% of the respondents had a family monthly income of below 5,000; 46 or 17.8% had a family monthly income of 6,000- 10,000; three or 1.2% had a family monthly income of 11,000- 15,000; and seven or 2.7% had a family month income of 16,000 above. Hence, majority of the respondents had a family monthly income of below 5,000, which is considered below the poverty line in terms of economic status. As regards academic performance of the students, four or 1.5% had a general grade average of 75-79; 54 or 20.8% had the general grade average of 80-84; 96 or 37.1% had the general grade average of 85-87; 79 or 30.5% had the general grade average of 88-90; 24 or 9.3% had the general grade average of 91-93; and only two or 0.8% had the general grade average of 94-96%. When the mean was computed, a value of 86.57 was arrived at and interpreted as satisfactory level of academic performance.

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents’ Profile

Profiles	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	150	57.9
	Female	109	42.1
Total		259	100
Age	18-19	89	34.4
	20-21	107	41.3
	22-23	40	15.4
	24 and above	23	8.9
Total		259	100
Program	BEEd	16	6.2
	BSBA	51	19.7
	BSCriminology	192	74.1
Total		259	100
Year Level	First Year	138	53.3
	Second Year	57	12.0
	Third Year	38	14.7
	Fourth Year	26	10.0
Total		259	100
Number of Enrolled Units	Below 18	39	15.1
	19-22	51	19.7
	23-26	60	23.2
	27 and above	109	42.1
Total		259	100
Monthly Income of the Family	Below ₱5,000	203	15.1
	₱6,000-10,000	46	19.7
	₱11,000-15,000	3	23.2
	₱16,000 above	7	42.1
Total		259	100
Academic Performance Mean=86.57	75-79	4	1.5
	80-84	54	20.8
	85-87	96	37.1
	88-90	79	30.5
	91-93	24	9.3
	94-96	2	0.8
Total		259	100

Table 2 exhibits the mean distribution of respondents according to stress-related factors namely personal/physical, interpersonal relationship, academic and environmental. These factors are the common stressors identified by Olape, et al. (2017), Essel & Owusu (2017) and Bulo & Sanchez (2014). In terms of personal/physical factor of stress, the frequent personal/physical stressors were sleep problems ($\bar{X}=2.58$) and excessive worry (2.51). Whereas, back pain ($\bar{X}=2.39$), headaches ($\bar{X}=2.36$), tiredness/fatigue ($\bar{X}=2.34$), sweating ($\bar{X}=2.32$), stomach pain ($\bar{X}=2.06$), frequent cold ($\bar{X}=2.04$), weight loss ($\bar{X}=2.03$), and difficulty breathing ($\bar{X}=1.85$) were somewhat frequent personal/physical stressors. According to Mazo (2015), sleep problems and excessive worry were the common personal/physical stressors that contributed stress. Likewise, Aspiras & Aspiras (2014) identified sleep problems as one of the top five stressors that contributed stress to the students. This personal/physical stressors could be a result of poor self-care habits and educational demands (Fogle, 2012) as well as due to their lifestyle (Bernal, 2017).

Regarding interpersonal relationship factor, the frequent interpersonal stressors were parent's support ($\bar{X}=3.35$) and guilt-feeling ($\bar{X}=2.78$). Whereas, peer interaction ($\bar{X}=2.44$), parent's expectations ($\bar{X}=2.25$), faculty mismanagement ($\bar{X}=2.17$), parent's treatment and unhealthy friendship ($\bar{X}=1.97$), relationship anxiety ($\bar{X}=1.91$), teacher's support ($\bar{X}=1.83$), and parent's support ($\bar{X}=1.75$) were the somewhat frequent interpersonal stressors. A study conducted by Essel and Owusu (2017) and Bulo and Sanchez (2014) identified that the interpersonal stressors like working to people they do not know, trouble with parents, and relationship with opposite sex were the major stressors among students. Yumba (2008) added that undergraduate students were commonly stressed because of interpersonal relationships with peers and on how they adjusted with the social network of the college. Similarly, Nuas, et al. (2015) stipulated that establishing new connections and dealing with people at the college were considered as the major stressors of the students. In contrary to these challenges brought by interpersonal relationship factors, it can be noted that strong social support and increased interpersonal contact can alleviate stress. Thus, positive and good social support from family, friends, and faculty can help to alleviate the stress that students may experience.

Relating to academic factor, the table reveals that the frequent academic stressors were financial problem ($\bar{X}=2.99$), feeling of embarrassment or humiliation ($\bar{X}=2.96$), time management between study and social activity ($\bar{X}=2.95$), examination stress ($\bar{X}=2.87$), work deadlines and subject difficulty ($\bar{X}=2.83$), time management between study and society involvement ($\bar{X}=2.78$), academic pressures ($\bar{X}=2.71$) and academic workloads ($\bar{X}=2.53$) while academic loss of interest was a somewhat frequent academic stressor. These findings show that most of the academic-related stressors had been frequently experienced by the respondents. These results affirm various researches wherein academic-related issues contribute massively to the level of stress of the students (Rana, 2019; Aspiras & Aspiras, 2014; Pfeiffer, 2001). Soomro, et al. (2019) stressed that class workload was the primary source of stress among students in relation to academic factors. This reason could be the primary factor wherein students had the difficulty of juggling their time and coping with various academic pressures. In addition, Saile, et al. (2015) identified academic stress as the top ranked stressors that include academic and class workload, grade, and examination.

As regards to environmental factor, the table displays that the frequent environmental stressors were unwanted sound ($\bar{X}=2.80$), uncomfortable feeling and lack of self-confidence ($\bar{X}=2.78$), unusual high temperature ($\bar{X}=2.77$), unpleasant environment ($\bar{X}=2.76$), crowded places ($\bar{X}=2.74$), pollution ($\bar{X}=2.70$), and transportation problem ($\bar{X}=2.51$). Whereas, inadequate facilities ($\bar{X}=2.46$) and bad living conditions ($\bar{X}=2.13$) were somewhat frequent environmental stressors. These findings signify that environmental stressors had been frequently experienced by the respondents. Environmental stressors are frequently experienced by the respondents as they play a major role in their lives. Yikealo, et al. (2018) identified various environmental stressors such as lack of transportation service, waiting in a long queue, exposed to disturbances, and inadequate school facilities were among the common factors that caused a higher level of environmental stress. In addition, various researches reported a significant level of relationship between environmental stressor and academic performance (Olape, et al., 2017; Essel & Owusu, 2017; Mushtaq & Khan, 2012).

Table 2 The Mean Distribution of Respondents According to Stress-Related Factors

Item Situations		Mean	Interpretation
On Personal/Physical Factors			
1.	Headaches	2.36	Somewhat Frequent
2.	Back pain	2.39	Somewhat Frequent
3.	Sleep problems	2.58	Frequent
4.	Difficulty breathing	1.85	Somewhat Frequent
5.	Excessive worry	2.51	Frequent
6.	Stomach pain/nausea	2.06	Somewhat Frequent
7.	Constant tiredness/fatigue	2.34	Somewhat Frequent
8.	Sweating/sweaty hands	2.32	Somewhat Frequent
9.	Frequent cold/flu/fever	2.04	Somewhat Frequent
10.	Drastic weight loss	2.03	Somewhat Frequent
On Interpersonal Relationship Factors			
11.	I found it difficult to meet my high parent’s expectations.	2.25	Somewhat Frequent
12.	My parents treated me as a helpless person.	1.97	Somewhat Frequent
13.	I felt guilty if I failed to fulfil my parent’s hope.	2.78	Frequent
14.	My parents wished only for my success.	3.35	Frequent
15.	I found it difficult to get along with group mates in doing academic task.	2.44	Somewhat Frequent
16.	My friends did not care about me.	1.97	Somewhat Frequent
17.	I felt disturbed when having problems with my boyfriend/girlfriend.	1.91	Somewhat Frequent
18.	My families were not supportive.	1.75	Somewhat Frequent
19.	My lecturers/teachers were not supportive.	1.83	Somewhat Frequent
20.	I felt frustrated due to the lack of faculty management.	2.17	Somewhat Frequent
On Academic Factors			
21.	I had a financial problem because of the expenses of the college.	2.99	Frequent
22.	I found it difficult to juggle time between study and social activity.	2.95	Frequent
23.	I felt nervous delivering class presentation.	2.96	Frequent
24.	I felt stressed as submission deadline neared.	2.83	Frequent
25.	I felt stressed to sit for examination.	2.87	Frequent
26.	I found it difficult to juggle time between study and society involvement.	2.78	Frequent
27.	I lost interest toward the courses I am taking.	2.22	Somewhat Frequent
28.	I felt burdened of academic workloads.	2.53	Frequent
29.	I felt stressed dealing with difficult subject.	2.83	Frequent
30.	I felt difficult in handling my academic problem.	2.71	Frequent
On Environmental Factors			
31.	I had transportation problem.	2.51	Frequent
32.	I felt stressed with bad living condition of the boarding house.	2.13	Somewhat Frequent
33.	Surrounding noise distracted me.	2.80	Frequent
34.	Pollution made me uneasy.	2.70	Frequent
35.	Hot weather made me avoid going out.	2.77	Frequent
36.	Messy living conditions distracted me.	2.76	Frequent
37.	I felt frustrated of inadequate school facilities.	2.46	Somewhat Frequent
38.	Crowded places made me feel uneasy.	2.74	Frequent
39.	Waiting in a long line made me feel uneasy.	2.78	Frequent
40.	I felt scared being in an insecure place.	2.78	Frequent

Table 3 presents the frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation distribution of respondents’ level of stress. The table shows that 82 or 31.7% of the respondents experienced mild level of stress; 94 or 36.3% of the respondents endured moderate level of stress; and 83 or 32% of the respondents exhibited severe level of stress. The

distribution’s mean score was 2.00 (SD=.800) interpreted as moderate level of stress. The results show that most (68.3%) of the respondents had experienced moderate to severe level of stress. These results were heavily influenced by academic and environmental stressors wherein eight out of ten situations were frequently experienced among the

respondents. Whereas, personal/physical and interpersonal stressors were somewhat frequently experienced by the respondents. These results conform to various researches wherein students showed moderate to severe level of stress (Hernández, et al., 2019; Saile, et al., 2017; Bernal, et al., 2017; Olape, et al., 2017; Bulo & Sanchez, 2014) .These findings imply that most of them had a hard time of coping

from various stressors. This could affect their well-being as well as mental stability and their academic performance. This adverse effect was evident to the respondents' academic performance wherein 37.1% performed satisfactorily and 22.3% performed fairly and just barely passed the semester.

Table 3 Respondents' Level of Stress

Level of Stress	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Standard Deviation
Mild Stress	82	31.7	2.00	.800
Moderate Stress	94	36.3		
Severe Stress	83	32.0		
Total	259	100		

Table 4 displays the results on the correlation between respondents' level of stress and their demographic profile. A Pearson Product Moment of Correlation coefficient was computed to assess the linear relationship between the variables. The results are as q:

➤ *On Significance of Relationship*

- There was no significant correlation of .058 ($p=ns$) between gender and level of stress, as did monthly income of the family ($p=.965, ns$).
- Age ($r=-.730$), program ($r=.283$), year level ($r=-.349$), number of enrolled units ($r=.536$) and academic performance ($r=-.537$) were significantly correlated, $p<.05$, with level of stress.

These results show that a negative correlation was found among respondents' age, year level, academic performance, and their level of stress. This finding signified that age, year level, academic performance of the respondents were inversely proportional to their level of stress. These findings imply that the respondents whose aged ranged from 18-19, were first year, and they had low academic performance which revealed that they had experienced severe level of stress.

Whereas, a positive correlation was found among respondents' collegiate program, number of enrolled units, and their level of stress. This finding signified that collegiate program and the number of enrolled units were directly proportional to their level of stress. These findings imply that the respondents who took Criminology and enrolled 27 and above units experienced severe level of stress.

Table 4 Results on the Correlation Between Respondents' level of Stress and their Demographic Profile

Variable	Level of Stress	Description
Gender	Pearson Correlation	-.118
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.058
Age	Pearson Correlation	-.730
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
Program	Pearson Correlation	.283
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
Year Level	Pearson Correlation	-.349
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
Number of Enrolled Units	Pearson Correlation	.536
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
Monthly Income of the Family	Pearson Correlation	-.003
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.965
Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	-.537
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000

Table 5 presents the results on relationship between respondents' level of stress and their demographic profile. Multiple regression analysis was used to investigate whether the profile of the respondents according to age, collegiate program, year level, number of enrolled units, and academic performance could significantly predict their level of stress. The results were as follows:

➤ *On Significant Predictors*

- The model explained 68.2% of the variance and the model was a significant predictor of level of stress, $F(5,253) = 108.667, p=.000$.
- It was found that age ($\beta = -.464, p<.000$), number of enrolled units ($\beta = .192, p<.000$), and academic performance ($\beta = -.236, p<.000$) significantly predicted respondents' level of stress.

These results show that based on collected quantitative data, three out of five independent variables tested namely age, number of enrolled units and academic performance significantly predicted respondents' level of stress. Both age and academic performance of the respondents showed a negative correlation. Whereas, a positive correlation was found in the number of enrolled units of the respondents. These findings imply that schools should plan and implement drastic measures to address the findings of this

study. The schools should intensify its instructional management from student's admission, delivery of the curriculum, assessment, and support systems. These measures could respond to the existing problems that hamper student's academic success and prevent future problems. If not, this problem will escalate and the well-being and mental stability of the students will be put into risk.

Table 5 Results on the Relationship Existed Between Respondents' level of Stress and their Demographic Profile

Independent Variable	B	Std. Error	t-ratio	Sig.	Interpretation
Age	-.464	.039	-11.497	.000	Significant
Program	-.047	.056	-.846	.399	Not Significant
Year Level	-.005	.032	-.154	.877	Not Significant
Number of Enrolled Units	.192	.030	6.461	.000	Significant
Academic Performance	-.236	.033	-7.126	.000	Significant
Constant			3.577		
		R ²	= .682		
		F-ratio	= 108.667	p < .05	
		SEE	= .453		
		N	= 259		

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the study, it can be inferred that out of the four stress-related factors, academic and environmental stressors were found contributing most to the stress level of the students.

- Gender and monthly income of the family had no significant correlation with the respondents' level of stress.
- Program and year level had a weak positive and negative correlation with the respondents' level of stress. Other demographic variables such as age and number of enrolled units had a positive and negative moderate to strong correlation with level of stress.
- Students' academic performance was inversely proportional to their stress level.
- Students' stress level and their academic performance implied a negative moderate correlation and produced sufficient evidence of statistically significant relationship.
- The profile of the students in terms of age, number of enrolled units, and academic performance significantly predicted their level of stress.
- The results of this study provided sufficient evidence that stress had negative effects on academic performance. Thus, the school's services and programs should support students academically to attain holistic student development.

➤ Recommendations

From the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are hereby presented:

- School Administrators should revisit school policies pertaining to the academic affairs of the students that are intimidating and unrealistic. School policies should help students to reach their full-capacity as a person not to reprimand students from performing at their best.
- Guidance Counsellors should create an effective and integrated guidance program that are proactive and realistic in nature to deeply understand students' situations and psychological state for them to utilize their potentials to the fullest. This should be done regularly to monitor students' well-being.
- Teachers should help students to cope up with stress. They should understand every aspect of the students for them to provide a holistic approach that develop students' self-esteem, enthusiasm, and courage in facing any adversities in life.
- Parents should monitor their children regularly. They should be the primary people that their children can rely with. In short, the parent should be the primary support system of their children.
- Students should be aware of the detrimental effects of stress. They should learn and identify effective coping mechanisms that could help them to overcome a stressful situation.
- Future researchers related to stress may gain more in-depth understanding and information of this study. The future researchers can also use this study as a reference. It is highly recommended to include other variables such as coping mechanisms.

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REFERENCES

- [1]. Aihie, O., & Ohanaka B. (2019). Perceived Academic Stress among Undergraduate Students in a Nigerian University. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, Vol. 9 No. 2 May 2019. Doi: 10.2478/jesr-2019-0013
- [2]. Alsubaie, M., Stain, H., Webster, L., & Wadman, R. (2019). The Role of Sources of Social Support on Depression and Quality of Life for University Students. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*, Volume 24, 13(1). DOI: 10.1080/02673843.2019.1568887
- [3]. American College Health Association (2012). American College Health Association: National College Health Assessment II Reference Group Executive Summary Spring 2012. Hanover, MD: American College Health Association; 2012.
- [4]. Aspiras, L., & Aspiras, E. (2014). Perceived Stress Factors and Academic Performance of the Sophomore IT Students of QSU Cabarroguis Campus. *International Conference on Economics, Education and Humanities (ICEEH)*, Dec. 10-11, 2014 Bali (Indonesia).
- [5]. Bernal, J.M., Caguimbal, J.G., Palatulan, J.R., Sahagun, R.M., & Simbulas, L.J. 2017. Level of Stress of Academic Performance of Selected College Students of the University of Immaculate Conception. *International Journal of Liberal Arts, Education, Social Sciences and Philosophical Studies*, Volume 5, No. 1, pp. 85-92.
- [6]. Bernstein, D.A., Penner, L.A., Stewart, A.C. and Roy, E.J. (2008). *Psychology* (8th edition). Houghton Mifflin Company Boston New York.
- [7]. Bulo, J.G., & Sanchez M.G. (2014). Sources of Stress among College Students. *CVCITC Research Journal*, 1 (1), pp 16 – 25.
- [8]. Cherian, V., & Charian, L. (1998). University Students Adjustment. *Psychological Reports*, 82, 1135-1138.
- [9]. Eduardo, J. & Panganoron, C. (2015). *Human Behavior & Crisis Management*. Wiseman's Books Trading, Inc.
- [10]. Essel, G., & Owusu, P. (2017). Causes of Students' Stress, Its Effects on their Academic Success, and Stress Management by Students. A Thesis at Seinäjoki University of Applied Sciences. Finland.
- [11]. Farabaugh, A., Bitran, S., Nyer, M., Holt, D.J., Pedrelli, P., Shyu, I., & Peterson, T.J. (2012). Depression and Suicidal Ideation in College Students. *Psychopathology*, 45(4), 228-234.
- [12]. Feldman, L., Goncalves, L., Chacon-Puignau, G., Zaragosa, G., Bages, N., & De Pablo, N. (2018). Relationships between Academic Stress, Social Support, Mental Health and Academic Performance in Venezuelan University Students. *Universitas Psychologica*, V. 7, No. 3, pp 739-751, Sept-Dec. 2008.
- [13]. Galindez-Vibar, M.L., & Galindez, E.M.V. (2011). *General Psychology for Criminology Students*. Philippine College of Criminology- Manila Law College (PCCR-MLC): Sta. Cruz, Manila.
- [14]. Hanson, P.G. (1987). *The Joy of Stress*. Hanson Stress Management Organization, Inc.: Canada.
- [15]. Hashim, I. H. (2003). Cultural and Gender Differences in Perceptions of Stressors and Coping Skill. A Study of Western and African College Student in China. *School Psychology International*, 24, 182-203.
- [16]. Hill, C. (2014). School Stress, Academic Performance, and Coping in College Freshmen. *Ursidae: The Undergraduate Research Journal at the University of Northern Colorado*: Vol. 4: No. 2, Article 9. <http://digscholarship.unco.edu/urj/vol4/iss2/9>
- [17]. Ibrahim, A.K., Kelly, S.J., Adams, C.E., & Glazebrook, C. (2013). A Systematic Review of Studies of Depression Prevalence in University Students. *Journal of Psychiatric Research*, 47(3), 391-400.
- [18]. Khanekhesi, Al. & Basavarajappa (2011). The Relationship of Academic Stress with Aggression, Depression and Academic Performance of College Students in Iran. *Journal on Educational Psychology*, Vol. 5, No. 1, May-July 2011.
- [19]. Kring, A.M., Davison, G.C., Neale, J.M., & Johnson, S.L. (2010). *Abnormal Psychology* (11th edition). Hoboken, NJ: Wiley.
- [20]. Kumari, M., Badrick, E., Chandola, T., Adam, E.K., Stafford, M., Marmot, M.G, et al. Cortisol Secretion and Fatigue: Associations in a Community Based Cohort. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*. 34: 1476-85.
- [21]. Lazarus, R.S. (1966). *Psychological Stress and Coping Process*. Mcgraw-Hill: New York.
- [22]. Lazarus, R.S., & Cohen, J.B. (1977). Environmental Stress. In I.altman and J.F. Wohlwill (eds.), *Human Behavior and Environment*. New York: Plenum.
- [23]. Lazarus. R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). *Stress Appraisal and Coping*. New York: Springer.
- [24]. Lemay, P. (1993). *Stress, Temperament, and Academic Achievement*. Open Access Dissertations. Paper 995. https://digitalcommons.uri.edu/oa_diss/995
- [25]. May, R. (2015). *The Meaning of Anxiety*. New York: W.W. Norton & Company Ltd.
- [26]. Mazo, G. (2015). Causes, Effects of Stress, and the Coping Mechanism of Political Science Students in a Philippine University. *International Journal of Education and Research*. Vol. 3 No. 2 February 2015.

- [27]. Mazo, G. (2015). Causes, Effects of Stress, and the Coping Mechanism of the Bachelor of Science in Information Technology Students in A Philippine University. *Journal of Education and Learning*. Vol. 9(1) pp. 71-78.
- [28]. McEwen, B.S. (2004). Protection and Damage from Acute and Chronic Stress: Allostasis and Allostatic Overload and Relevance to the Pathophysiology of Psychiatric Disorders. *Annual Journal of New York Academy of Sciences*, 1032: 1-7.
- [29]. Melgosa, J. (2004). *Less Stress*. Madrid: Editorial Safelix, S. L.
- [30]. Mire, R., & McKean, M. (2000). College Student's Academic Stress and its Relation to their Anxiety, Time Management and Leisure Satisfaction. *American Journal of Health Studies*, 120(1), 41-51.
- [31]. Mustafa, B. (2004). Assessment of Academic Stress and Its Impact on Academic Performance and Adjustment of the Students. A Thesis at Aligarh Muslim University, Department of Psychology, Aligarh, India.
- [32]. Nuas, A., Mercado, C., Matanguihan, C.O., Roper, M-A., Dumaoal, O.S., & Flores, M.S. 2015. Stressors and Coping Mechanism of Physical Therapy Students of Lyceum of the Philippines University- Batangas. *The Steth*, Vol. 9, 2015.
- [33]. Okoro, E. (2018). Assessment of Stress Related Issues & Coping Mechanisms among College Students. A Thesis at Minnesota State University. Mankato, Minnesota. All Theses, Dissertations, and Other Capstone Projects. 825. <https://cornerstone.lib.mnsu.edu/etds/825>
- [34]. Olape, O.R., A. Yahaya L., Chiaka, A.E., & Abidoye, T.K. (2017). Stress Level and Academic Performance of University Students in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Makerere Journal of Higher Education*, 9 (1) (2017) 103-112. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/majohe.v9i1.9>
- [35]. Palacio, O.M., Palacio, A.M., Blanco, Y.O.V., Palacio, M.M., & Roblejo, Y.P. (2013). Academic Stress: Causes and Consequences. *Multimed*, 17(2), 185-196.
- [36]. Peralta, E.P.D., Botor, N.J.B., & Laude, T.M.P. (2019). *A Course Module for Gender and Society: A Human Ecological Approach* (1st edition). Rex Book Store, Inc.: Sampaloc, Manila.
- [37]. Pereira, A.M. (1997). *Helping Students Cope: Peer Counselling in Higher Education* (Doctoral dissertation). Retrieved from: <https://ethos.bl.uk/OrderDetails.do?uin=uk.bl.ethos.363281>
- [38]. Petroff, L.L. (2008). Stress, Adult Attachment, and Academic Success among Community College Students. *Public Access Theses and Dissertations from the College of Education and Human Sciences*, 27. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cehsdiss/27>
- [39]. Pfeiffer, D. (2001). Academic and Environmental Stress among Undergraduate College Students: A Literature Review. A Research Paper. University of Wisconsin-Stout. Menomonie, WI 54751.
- [40]. Phinney, J.S. & Haas, K. (2003). The Process of Coping among Ethnic Minority First Generation College Freshmen: A Narrative Approach. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, Vols. 143(6), 707–726.
- [41]. Puyat, J.H., Gastardo-Conaco, M.C., Natividad, J., & Banal, M.A. (2020). Depressive Symptoms among Young Adults in the Philippines: Results from a Nationwide Cross-Sectional Survey. *Journal of Affective Disorders Reports*, Volume 3 (2021) 100073. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadr.2020.100073>
- [42]. Rana, A., Gulati, R., & Wadhwa V. (2019). Stress Among Students: An Emerging Issue. *Integrated Journal of Social Sciences*, 2019, 6(2), 44-48.
- [43]. Reddy, K., Karishmarajanmenon, & Anjanathattil (2018). Academic Stress and its Sources among University Students. *Biomedical & Pharmacology Journal*, Vol. 11(1), 531-537 (2018). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13005/bpj/1404>
- [44]. Roth, T. (2007). Insomnia: Definition, Prevalence, Etiology, and Consequences. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine*, Aug 15; Volume 3(5 Suppl):S7-S10.
- [45]. Saile, P.J., Daan, J.A., Briones, E., Tabotabo, J., Ramo, C., & Canini, D. 2017. Stress, Coping Strategies, and Academic Performance of Maritime Students. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Students*, Vol. 6, Issue No. 1, pp. 74-92, August 2017. <http://dx.doi.org/10.7828/jmids.v6i1.1036>
- [46]. Sarafino, E.P. (2002). *Health Psychology: Biopsychosocial Interactions* (4th Ed.). New York, NY, USA: John Wiley & Sons, Inc; 2002.
- [47]. Simpson, S. (2018). Stress Triggers, the Effects Stress Has on Social, Mental and Physical Behavior in College Students, and the Coping Mechanisms Used. *Integrated Studies*. 215. <https://digitalcommons.murraystate.edu/bis437/215>
- [48]. Smith, L., Kenneth, E., & Sinclair (1998). Stress and Learning in the Higher School Certificate. *The University of Study, Journal Articles*.
- [49]. Soomro, M.A., Soomro, M., Mahesar, G., & Rani, S. (2019). A Study of Stress Factors and their Impact on Students' Academic Performance at University Level. *Grassroots*, Vol.53, No. 1
- [50]. Stankovska, G., Dimitrovski, D., Angelkoska, S., Ibraimi, Z., & Uka, V. (2018). Emotional Intelligence, Test Anxiety and Academic Stress among University Students. *Education in Modern Society*, BCES Conference Books, 2018, Volume 16. Sofia: Bulgarian Comparative Education Society.
- [51]. Suleyman, M., & Zewdu, A. (2018). Prevalence and Associated Factors of Stress among Undergraduate Students in Ambo University: Implication for Intervention. *International Journal of Psychology and Counselling*, Vol. 10(4), pp. 29-39, September 2018. DOI: 10.5897/IJPC2018.0532
- [52]. Tyrrel, J. (1992). Sources of Stress among Psychology Undergraduates. *Irish Journal of Psychology*, 13, 184-192.
- [53]. Whitman, N., Spendlove, D., & Clarck, C. (1984). *Student Stress: Effects & Solutions*.

- [54]. Yikealo, D., Yemane, B., & Karvinen, I. (2018). The Level of Academic and Environmental Stress among College Students: A Case in the College of Education. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 6, 40-57. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jss.2018.611004>
- [55]. Yumba, W. (2008). *Academic Stress: A Case of the Undergraduate Students*. Linköping University: Institutionen för Beteendevetenskap Och Lärande. Linköping, Sweden.
- [56]. *Zimbardo, P., Weber, A., & Johnson, R. (2003). Psychology Core Concepts*. Publisher's Design & Production Services, Inc. Allyn & Bacon: Boston, MA 02115.